

Circles of mutual aid

by Pablo Angel Lugo

Circles of mutual aid

This series of drawings is part of the exercises I am working on to change the idea of schemas. The schema is the visual way to explain how different concepts are related to each other, and this is a cartography of ideas. I am developing this idea of linking concepts. The idea of people helping each other is very appealing, and graphically displaying that idea is just beautiful.

Mutual Aid is one of the three fundamental concepts in anarchy. Helping each other in different situations will help people to create a better social fabric. Anarchy is that way to understand that circle of Mutual Aid, that old idea of today for you, tomorrow for me. A circle in human behaviour is not always something perfect. Circles are formed by patterns which are not equal, people are not the same, but their behaviour towards other people is continuously changing and being challenged.

If we can figure out those actions, different than our own, we will be able to understand similitude between others and ourselves. Our space, knowledge and humanity limit us by itself.

Circles of Mutual Aid I

Ballpoint pen on paper, 40 x 30 cm

2018

Circles of Mutual Aid II

Ballpoint pen on paper, 40 x 30 cm

2018

Circles of Mutual Aid III

Ballpoint pen on paper, 40 x 30 cm

2018

Circles of Mutual Aid IV

Ballpoint pen on paper, 40 x 30 cm

2018

Circles of Mutual Aid V

Ballpoint pen on paper, 40 x 30 cm

2018

Circles of Mutual Aid VI

Ballpoint pen on paper, 40 x 30 cm

2018

Circles of Mutual Aid VII

Ballpoint pen on paper, 40 x 30 cm

2018

Circles of Mutual Aid VIII

Ballpoint pen on paper, 40 x 30 cm

2018

Circles of Mutual Aid IX

Ballpoint pen on paper, 40 x 30 cm

2018

Pablo Angel Lugo is an artist of considerable international reputation and enviable academic background, born in Mexico City. His work has taken him worldwide and been exhibited likewise.

Pablo's speciality is in public art, but his vast artistic output includes paintings, drawings, engravings, sculptures, videos, performances, illustrations, graphic designs and cinematic collaborations.

His work has been exhibited in Mexico, Cuba, USA, UK, Spain, Colombia, France, Portugal, Argentina and Indonesia amongst other countries.

He has studied in Mexico and Spain, earning a BA in Visual Arts and an MA and an MPhil in Public Art, he is currently completing his PhD in Public Art supported by a scholarship from the Jumex Foundation.

He is a veteran of many courses and workshops and also teaches both in the UK and overseas in his areas of speciality. Pablo is a member of some professional associations and a founding member of the Free University Collective of Art Theory and Research, the Circular Workshop of Graphic Production, the Autonomous Gallery in the National School of Plastic Arts and of the self-managed cultural centre The Three in Valencia.

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